

Chemistry of Ketoanil and Thiourea or Chloro-substituted-amine Complexes of Cobalt(II) and Platinum(IV)

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Manuscript received 7 October 1994, revised 14 June 1995, accepted 13 September 1995

Although inorganic ligand(s) substituted ammine complexes have been often worked out but products obtained by partial or complete replacement of strongly coordinated ammonia by neutral organic donor molecules, including ketoanils, alone and alongwith inorganic ligands, viz. water, halide etc., have been rarely explored¹⁻³. Therefore, complexes obtained by replacement of ammonia of amine complexes of cobalt(II) or/and platinum(IV) with thiophene-2-glyoxal-2-mercaptylanil (1), C₄H₃SCOCH=N-C₆H₄-SH-*o*, thiophene-2-glyoxal-2-pyridineanil (2), C₄H₃SCOCH=N-C₅H₄N-*o*, or thiophene-2-glyoxal-2-pyrimidineanil (3), C₄H₃SCOCH=N-C₄H₃N₂-*o*, and thiourea and/or chloro, which have not been described as yet, have been synthesised and reported in the present communication. A few of the products, isolated as binary mixtures, have been resolved by column chromatography.

Results and Discussion

The analytical and molar conductance data of complexes (Table 1), which agree well with their structural formulations, suggest water molecule(s) in them. Lattice water exhibits symmetric and antisymmetric stretching and bending vibrations at 3 060-3 460 and 1 580-1 630 cm⁻¹ respectively, whereas coordinated water which shows twisting, wagging or rocking vibrations at 935-1 015 cm⁻¹ displays one, two or three M-O stretching bands at 230-410 cm⁻¹. Aquo-complexes are highly soluble in coordinating solvents like pyridine and DMSO. Although, ir studies could not differentiate between hydroxyl group and water molecule in and out of coordination sphere of the hydroxyl complexes, their presence, however, has been indicated by molar conductance and analytical data.

Lowering in ir frequencies of C=N and C-S groups of thiophene-2-glyoxal-2-mercaptylanil on complexation from 1 620 and 870 and 845 cm⁻¹ to ~1 593 and 853 cm⁻¹, and the new bands at ~527 and ~289 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the complexes, attributable to ν_{M-N} and ν_{M-S} respectively, show coordination of these groups of ligand with metal ions. Undisturbed position of ν_{SH} ligand peak (2 320 cm⁻¹) in the complexes, however, indicates^{3,4} coordination of unionised SH group, owing to its intramolecular H-bonding with azomethine nitrogen, as also suggested by molar conductance data.

Although appearance of bands^{3,4} for $\nu_{C=N}$, $\nu_{C=C}$ aromatic, ring breathing, ϕ C-C and C-C deformation of thiophene-2-glyoxal-2-pyridineanil (1630, 1590 and 1 070,

1 040 and 980, 725, and 405 cm⁻¹) and thiophene-2-glyoxal-2-pyrimidineanil (1 665, and 1 575 and 1 500 and 1 085, 1 065, 1 050 and 980, 720 (doublet), and 430 cm⁻¹) at different frequencies, ~1 604 and 1 571 and 1 518, and 1 080, 1 043 and 1 008, 713, and 409, and at 1 640, and 1 570 and 1 516 and 1 071, 1 021 and 980, and 756 and 713 cm⁻¹, and 423 cm⁻¹, in the spectra of their complexes respectively, indicates³ coordination of azomethine and heterocyclic nitrogens of both the ligands, but two new peaks or a broad peak composed by two peaks of small frequency difference for ν_{M-N} observed at 450-590 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the complex, confirm this conclusion.

Doublet or broad peak structure of one of the ν_{M-N} peaks in the complexes obtained by partial substitution of ketoanil in platinum amine complex, a single peak at 480 cm⁻¹ in [Pt(SCN₂H₄)(NH₃)(OH)₄], and free NH₂ and N-H stretching vibrations at ~3 340 and ~3 135 cm⁻¹ owe to coordination of NH₃. In the complexes involving SCN₂H₄ and ketoanil/NH₃, unperturbed amine frequencies and a new low frequency band at 235-305 cm⁻¹, however, indicate coordination of SCN₂H₄ through sulphur. On the basis of undisturbed position of carbonyl and thienyl groups bands of the ketoanils in their complex spectra, coordination of these groups of ligands is ruled out. Presence of chlorine in the coordination sphere indicated by one or two ir-active M-Cl bands at 290-380 cm⁻¹ was supported by the molar conductance values of the complexes.

Observed diamagnetism of the platinum(IV) complexes indicates their low-spin octahedral geometry. Electronic spectral bands at ~16 699, 19 922, 21 942 and 28 044 cm⁻¹, corresponding to ${}^3T_{1g} \leftarrow {}^1A_{1g}$, ${}^3T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^1A_{1g}$, ${}^1T_{1g} \leftarrow {}^1A_{1g}$ and ${}^1T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^1A_{1g}$ respectively, are also consistent with low-spin octahedral geometry. Magnetic moments of the cobalt(II) complexes are characteristic of their high-spin octahedral geometry. Two or three bands at ~12 448, 15 853 and 18 563 cm⁻¹, attributed to ${}^2E_g \leftarrow {}^4T_{1g}$, ${}^4A_{2g} \leftarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ and $b^4T_{1g} \leftarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ respectively, displayed by electronic spectra, support the magnetic inference. Values of ligand field parameters, 10 *Dq*, Reclan's parameters (*B* and *C*) and β , obtained by standard methods^{5,6} are listed in Table 1. Greater separation of the *d-d* transitions in [Co(C₁₁-H₈N₂SO)(H₂O)₄]Cl₂.2H₂O (a) than that in [Co(C₁₁-H₈N₂SO)(H₂O)₄]Cl₂.2H₂O (b) indicates^{2,7} *cis*-symmetry for *a*-isomer and *trans* for the *b*-compound.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA AND LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS OF COMPLEX

Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	λ_M $\Omega^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$	μ_{eff} B.M.	10Dq cm^{-1}	B	C	β	
[Co ₂ (C ₁₂ H ₉ NS ₂ O) ₂ Cl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₂]	(c) Gray	240	10.3	(non)	4.98	8 230	902.0	3 517.8	0.81
[Co(C ₁₂ H ₉ NS ₂ O)Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂].2H ₂ O	(d) Green	150	8.2	(non)	5.09	8 025	695.9	2 714.0	0.62
[Co ₂ (C ₁₂ H ₉ NS ₂ O) ₂ (SCN ₂ H ₄) ₂ Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂	Green	230	181.8	(1 : 2)	5.03	8 093	832.9	3 248.3	0.74
[Pt(C ₁₂ H ₉ NS ₂ O)Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O	Brown	160	162.9	(1 : 2)	Diam.	24 780	381.2	2 307.5	—
[Pt(SCN ₂ H ₄)(NH ₃)(OH) ₄]	Brown	225	10.4	(non)	—	—	—	—	—
[Pt(C ₁₂ H ₉ NS ₂ O)(SCN ₂ H ₄)Cl ₂ (H ₂ O)]Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O	Orange	220	199.8	(1 : 2)	Diam.	23 913	377.4	2 174.0	—
[Co(C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ SO)(H ₂ O) ₄].Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O	(a) Pink	300	198.1	(1 : 2)	5.11	8 225	875.7	3 415.2	0.78
[Co(C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ SO)(H ₂ O) ₄]Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O	(b) Green	200	234.1	(1 : 2)	5.06	7 833	726.3	2 832.6	0.65
[Co(C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ SO)(SCN ₂ H ₄)Cl ₂ (H ₂ O)]	(c) Brown	>320	15.7	(non)	4.96	10 030	865.0	3 373.5	0.77
[Co(C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ SO) ₂ (SCN ₂ H ₄)Cl]Cl.H ₂ O	(d) Red	105	83.2	(1 : 1)	5.07	8 225	875.7	3 415.2	0.78
[Pt(C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ SO) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O	Yellow	178	261.6	(1 : 2)	Diam.	24 412	401.9	2 673.0	—
[Pt(C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ SO)(NH ₃) ₄](OH) ₄ .H ₂ O	Gray	>300	523.1	(1 : 4)	—	—	—	—	—
[Pt(C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ SO) ₂ (SCN ₂ H ₄) ₄]Cl ₄ .6H ₂ O	Gray	205	587.8	(1 : 4)	Diam.	24 561	396.8	2 339.0	—
[Co(C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₃ SO) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O	Yellow	130	204.6	(1 : 2)	5.13	9 029	840.4	3 277.6	0.75
[Co(C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₃ SO) ₂ (SCN ₂ H ₄)Cl]Cl ₃ .3H ₂ O	(a) Brown	140	91.1	(1 : 1)	5.10	8 735	819.0	3 194.1	0.73
[Co(C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₃ SO)(SCN ₂ H ₄)Cl(H ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₄ .4H ₂ O	(b) Green	215	63.9	(1 : 1)	5.15	8 025	695.9	2 714.0	0.62
[Pt(C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₃ SO) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₄	Yellow	125	561.3	(1 : 4)	Diam.	24 916	377.4	3 177.0	—
[Pt(C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₃ SO)(NH ₃) ₄]Cl ₄ .H ₂ O	Orange	210	561.6	(1 : 4)	—	—	—	—	—
[Pt(C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₃ SO)(SCN ₂ H ₄) ₄]Cl ₄ .2H ₂ O	Gray	160	592.7	(1 : 4)	Diam.	24 796	353.6	3 057.0	—

Experimental

Thiophene-2-glyoxal-2-mercaptyl-2-, -pyridine- and -2-pyrimidine-anils were prepared by known method³. Hexaammine platinum chloride complex, [Pt(NH₃)₆]Cl₄, precipitated on adding NH₃ to acetonic solution of chloroplatinic acid was washed with acetone and dried in an air oven (70 ± 5°). Chloroplatinic acid (Johnson Matthey) and other chemicals (B.D.H.) were used as supplied.

Preparation of the complexes: Ketoanil and/or thiourea substituted amine complexes of Pt^{IV} were prepared by mixing equimolar amounts of ligand and amine complex in DMF in presence of NH₃ (20 cm³), refluxing the mixture on a water-bath for 1 h, extracting the product with ether and precipitating with acetone after concentrating the extract. [Pt(NH₃)(SCN₂H₄)(OH)₄], however, was precipitated by adding Me₂CO to the mixture of [Pt(NH₃)₆]Cl₄ (1 mol), SCN₂H₄ (1 mol) and NH₃ (10 cm³) in water after heating on a water-bath for 30 min.

Mixed ligand complexes of Pt^{IV} with ketoanil and/or thiourea or aquo or chloro ligands were precipitated on mixing equimolar amounts of chloroplatinic acid and ketoanil and/or thiourea or HCl (1 cm³; 10%) in acetone in appropriate ratio. Products were washed with ether and acetone or water and dried in an oven (75 ± 5°). These complexes could not be prepared by replacement procedure as complete substitution of coordinated ammonia with either one or more ligands was found to be impossible probably due to their bigger size than NH₃.

The complexes of Co^{II} with ketoanil and/or thiourea or aquo or chloro ligands were prepared by mixing equimolar amounts of ketoanil alone or alongwith thiourea and HCl (1 cm³, 10%) with CoCl₂ in 2 : 1 ratio. Reaction mixtures, after refluxing for 1–2 h, were concentrated and the products obtained either by crystallisation or by precipitation with ether were washed with ether and acetone or water and dried in an oven (75 ± 5°).

Resolution of binary complexes: A few of the products, revealed as binary mixtures by tlc (on starch-bound silica gel layers) were resolved in bulk by column chromatography conducted in column containing silica gel (50–100 mesh, B.D.H.) using Me₂CO. Acetonic solutions of the products with a- and b-components were loaded, and the fast moving (b) component was eluted. Low R_F, slow moving component (a) of [Co(C₁₁H₈N₂SO)(H₂O)₄]Cl₂.2H₂O was eluted with EtOH, whereas [Co(C₁₀H₇N₃SO)(SCN₂H₄)(H₂O)₂]Cl₄.4H₂O (b) was eluted with DMF. Eluates were evaporated to dryness at ~50° at reduced pressure.

Binary products consisting of acetone insoluble (c) and soluble (d) components were resolved by treating with acetone and filtering the insoluble solid, and the residue obtained on evaporation of filtrate was dried at 50 ± 2°.

C, H and N were estimated microanalytically. Conductance of complexes in DMF was measured on a Toshniwal conductivity bridge. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (DMF) on a Spectronic 20 spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility of powdered solids was determined with a Gouy balance at room temperature (300 K).

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